

1 **Resistance to trastuzumab in HER2+ breast cancer is associated with re-activation of CDK6.**

2
3 Shahan K. Mamoor¹
4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
5 Chestnut Hill, MA 02467
6 East Islip, MA 11730

7 We demonstrate here from the measurement of total transcription using an *in vitro* experimental
8 system that models trastuzumab resistance at the clonal level that the cyclin dependent kinase CDK6 is
9 transcriptionally activated in HER2+ breast cancer cells following exposure to HER2+-targeted monoclonal
10 antibody trastuzumab, indicating the specific utility of CDK4/6 pharmacologic inhibition with the -ciclib
11 family (palbociclib, ribociclib and abemaciclib) in humans with HER2+ breast cancer.
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

- 1 1. We recently proposed the use of the *-cyclib* family of CDK4/6 inhibitors in conjunction with PARP1
- 2 *-parib* for the treatment of solid tumors of the breast and lung (1).
- 3 2. We described the utility of CDK4/6 inhibitors in treatment of a) metastasis to the lung and b)
- 4 metastasis to the central nervous system in humans with breast cancer, where CDK4 was activated (2, 3).
- 5 3. We demonstrated that pharmacologic CDK4/6 inhibition antagonizes induction of the interleukin
- 6 enhancer factors ILF2 and ILF3 resulting from re-activation of the estrogen-repressible non-coding RNA
- 7 Xist following treatment with endocrine therapy in patients with hormone receptor positive (HR+) luminal A
- 8 and luminal B breast cancer (4).
- 9 4. Moreover, we described a novel mechanism by which modulation of the semaphorin family of
- 10 genes with neurodevelopmental functions in axon guidance is modulated in human breast and human lung
- 11 cancer, and that pharmacologic CDK4/6 inhibition muted semaphorin family expression, which was
- 12 correlated with adverse patient survival outcomes (5).

13 Here, we studied cell cycle dynamics in HER2+ breast cancer, using an *in vitro* model of

14 trastuzumab resistance.

15 **An experimental system that models trastuzumab resistance *in vitro* at the clonal level reveals**

16 **CDK6 is activated in trastuzumab resistant breast cancer cells.**

17 **GSE15043**

18 n=2 wild-type BT474 cells

19 n=8 4 separate *in vitro* generated trastuzumab resistance clones (BT474) n=2 each

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
224848_at	9.34E-02	-1.82	-4.709009	-2.26E-01	CDK6	9944/54675 =	81.8

20 Thus, data from an *in vitro* system modeling trastuzumab resistance at the clonal level in HER2+

21 breast cancer cells demonstrated CDK6 was activated in HER2+ breast cancer following subtype-specific

22 treatment resulting in treatment resistance, indicating a molecular mechanism for the utility of

23 pharmacologic inhibition of CDK4/6 with the *-cyclibs* in HER2+ breast cancer.

24

25

26

27

28

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Mamoor, S. 2024. Use of a novel dual chemotherapy, a PARP1 inhibitor in conjunction with a CDK4/6 inhibitor, for treatment of solid tumors of the breast and lungs in humans.
2. Mamoor, S. 2024. CDK4 is activated in lung metastasis in human breast cancer.
3. Mamoor, S. 2024. CDK4 is activated in central nervous system metastasis in human breast cancer.
4. Mamoor, S. 2024. CDK4/6 inhibition with -cyclib (palbociclib, ribociclib, and abemaciclib) antagonizes Xist-associated interleukin enhancer factor ILF3 activation in hormone positive (HR+) breast cancer resulting from endocrine therapy.
5. Mamoor, S. 2024. Xist modulates semaphorin expression in solid tumors altering CNS outcomes, and pharmacological CDK4/6 inhibition antagonizes this function.